

Synthesis of 2-Cyano-3-(2'-furanyl)acrylamides as Potential Herbicides

RITU JINDAL and M. S. BHATIA*

Department of Chemistry, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana-141 004

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Compounds possessing amide linkage unsaturation and substituted aromatic heterocyclic systems are effective as herbicides. In continuation of our earlier work¹ on the synthesis of potential herbicides, a number of structures carrying such moieties have been synthesised and tested against two different weeds.

2-Cyano-3-(2'-furanyl)acrylic acid (1) was prepared by reacting cyanoacetic acid with furfural in the presence of ammonium acetate. The acid was further treated with different amines, viz. cyclohexylamine, morpholine, 4-aminophenazone, ethylamine, n-butylamine, n-hexylamine, in presence of phosphorus oxychloride and triethylamine to get the corresponding amides (2-7). The structural assignments of the compounds were based on their ir, nmr and mass spectral data².

Compounds 1-7 were evaluated for their herbicidal activity³ against two weeds, viz., *Trianthema portulacastrum* and *Echinochloa crusgalli* at different concentrations (0, 100, 200, 300, 400 and 500 ppm). Most of the compounds showed little activity against *E. crusgalli* but all the compounds showed maximum activity against *T. portulacastrum*. By considering the relative activity of compounds 1-7, the herbicidal activity decreased in the order: 5 > 6 > 7 > 1 > 4 > 2 > 3. The activity of compound 5 was highest as it completely inhibited the germination, root length and shoot length of *Trianthema* sp.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined by open capillary method and are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 800 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra on a EM/390 (90 MHz) spectro-

meter and mass spectra (70 eV) on a VG-Analytical-11-2505-70-S-spectrometer. All the compounds showed satisfactory elemental analysis and spectral data.

2-Cyano-3-(2'-furyl)acrylic acid (1): A mixture of cyanoacetic acid (8.5 g), ammonium acetate (0.3 g) and furfural (9.6 g) in dry benzene was refluxed for 10 h in a continuous water extracting apparatus. After cooling, the reaction mixture was washed with water. After drying the organic portion over anhydrous sodium sulphate, the solvent was evaporated and the resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol, (53%, 5.6 g), m.p. 210–12°.

N-Substituted-2-cyano-3(2'-furyl)acrylamides (2–7). *General procedure*: To an ice-cold mixture of the acid (**1**; 0.01 mol), triethylamine (0.0035 mol) and the corresponding amine (0.01 mol) dissolved in dry dichloromethane (50 ml), was added dropwise a solution of POCl₃ (0.01 mol) in dichloromethane (20 ml). Triethylamine (0.75 g, 0.007 mol) was added in one lot and stirred for 0.5 h at 0° and further 8 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was decomposed in crushed ice and extracted with dichloromethane. The extract was washed with saturated solution of sodium carbonate, water, HCl (10%) and finally with water. After drying the organic portion over anhydrous calcium chloride, the solvent was evaporated. The crude product was

chromatographed over silica gel using petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and chloroform mixture (1 : 3) as eluent to obtain the pure amides: **2** (34%), m.p. 74–76°; **3** (42%), 68–70°; **4** (25%), 115–16°; **5** (56%), 80–82°; **6** (48%), 47°; **7** (42%), 75–77°.

Ir spectra of compounds **2–7** showed peaks at 3 220–3 420 (NH), 2 220–2 235 (C≡N) and 1 610–1 647 cm⁻¹ (C=O). Nmr spectra exhibited signals at δ 6.25–8.7 (NH exchanged with D₂O), 8.16–8.26 (s, -CHCN-) and 6.76–7.83 (protons of furan system). Aromatic protons in case of compound **4** were present at δ 7.56, and -NCH₃ and =C-CH₃ protons at δ 2.26 and 3.16 respectively, as singlets. Methylene protons of compounds **2, 3** and **5** and **6** appeared as usual.

References

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